

Towards adaptive sustainable scheduling within lithium-ion battery production

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1 An introduction to adaptive scheduling

The rapid electrification of mobility and renewable energy integration have placed unprecedented demand on the large-scale production of lithium-ion batteries. Within this complex landscape, BATTwin¹ aims to revolutionize the battery manufacturing industry by developing a Digital Twin Platform that supports a digitally enhanced, zero-defect approach. The project emphasizes knowledge-based and explainable decision-making, scalability across production volumes, and robustness across battery chemistries. Among these challenges, the Flexible Job Shop Scheduling Problem (FJSP) stands out as a core decision-making task. Modern factories no longer seek only to minimize makespan; they must also ensure quality assurance, resource efficiency, and sustainability. The integration of digital twin feedback into scheduling optimization allows production systems to adapt dynamically to deviations, equipment conditions, or operator performance. This coupling transforms scheduling from a static pre-planning exercise into an adaptive decision process driven by continuously updated process knowledge [1].

Recent research in production scheduling has shifted from efficiency-focused optimization to multi-objective, human-aware decision models, considering energy, cost, and quality alongside makespan. Hybrid metaheuristics and multi-objective evolutionary strategies have been developed to efficiently explore complex solution spaces. Advances in AI and Digital Twin technologies now enable real-time feedback loops, where simulated system responses guide adaptive scheduling and closed-loop optimization [2]. Despite progress, challenges remain in explainability, scalability, and integration with real-world systems, motivating hybrid frameworks that combine mathematical optimization with learning-based, simulation-informed models for intelligent and sustainable production planning.

Therefore, in this study, we address the integrated challenge of incorporating a digital twin into a quality- and energy-aware flexible job shop scheduling framework with operator allocation constraints, aiming to evaluate its ability to balance performance, quality, and sustainability within modern, data-enhanced manufacturing environments. More scientifically, this study seeks to answer the following questions: What specific insights can the digital twin model provide? What measurable improvements can be expected from its integration? And how should its real-time feedback be systematically embedded within the optimization model to establish a closed-loop, adaptive decision-making system?

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2 Adaptive scheduling framework description and application

In modern era, a key advancement is the use of data-driven models that leverage historical production data to learn latent patterns. Digital twin models can capture complex, nonlinear dependencies between scheduling decisions and production outcomes, allowing systems to predict how sequences of operations, machine assignments, and operator allocations influence overall performance. In this regard, FIG 1 shows a schematic workflow integrating a Digital Twin with the optimization model. Orders are first processed by the optimization model, which considers constraints and objectives. The Digital Twin/Simulation layer evaluates potential schedules, providing insights about machine performance, process dynamics, and operator allocation. Real-time production feedback is then fed back into both the optimization and digital twin, creating a closed-loop system that continuously updates and refines scheduling decisions. This combination of AI, simulation, and real-time feedback enables robust, scalable, and explainable scheduling solutions, addressing challenges of multi-objective optimization in flexible manufacturing systems.

FIG. 1 – Adaptive scheduling framework.

FIG. 2 – An exemplary optimal scheduling plan

For instance, FIG 2 illustrates an optimal scheduling solution for a simple example with three jobs and three operations each. Here, digital twin-assisted scheduling can identify sequences that minimize the makespan, reduce energy consumption, and maximize quality, considering both machine capabilities and operator constraints. This visualizes how scheduling decisions can be optimized holistically rather than purely sequentially. From the proposed plan, for example, we can deduce that the first task of job J2 is scheduled at stage S1, executed by machine M1, with operator Op4 assigned to carry it out efficiently.

3 Conclusions and perspectives

This study studied the increasing complexity of modern manufacturing scheduling, where efficiency, quality, and sustainability must be jointly optimized under flexible machine and operator constraints. Integrating real-time feedback from digital twins into optimization frameworks has emerged as a powerful approach, enabling adaptive and data-informed decision-making. By combining exact methods and metaheuristics, such frameworks can navigate the multi-objective landscape of contemporary production systems effectively. Looking forward, the adoption of surrogate models offers a promising alternative to further enhance performance. By approximating expensive simulations or high-fidelity digital twin responses, surrogate models can significantly reduce computational costs while maintaining solution accuracy.

References

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